

>>Did the Dæther¹ respond?
>>Was that the dataleylines?!?

In this letter:

- Small update from Monday's publishing on MIMS 2.1.212a
- Sudden influx of money in the account we are tracking? Goes along with crypto rising?

MIMS 2.1.212b - Fibonacci Pressure vs Channel bounce

MIMS 2.5.1b - Financial Velocity Yields a Nugget?

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Small 2.5.1 update (b)

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¹ https://www.academia.edu/67236577/MIMS_2_102_In_pursuit_of_the_Daether

Re: What happens if “fibonacci² pressure” meets a spiral or channel bounce? New tracements

From the Desk of Sf. Ramon Careaga, founder EPEMC, www.epemcgateway.com

Dear Readers,

Figure 1 - Bitcoin Futures, pressure in channels? credit: Thinkorswim/author

Note the selloff at red fan, then the takeoff after bouncing off the new yellow fan.

² Remember, the 0 1 1 2 3 5 8 13 sequence is a key to the EPEMC, MIMS, and Big G diagram framework, and this is an important example of self-consistency.
https://www.academia.edu/53713967/MIMS_1_12_Self_Consistency_of_the_Big_G_Diagram
https://www.academia.edu/65563310/MIMS_1_01_03_Philosophy_Integration_Self_test

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Figure 2 - It was decided on the AIM call that there was likely to be upward pressure. I wrote this sentence now at 12:23 PM EST 1/13/22

Let's get a new graphical export that is 2 days newer

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Figure 3 - I've added fibonacci cycles on Tuesday, and today, Thursday it shows interesting interactions. The red fans are slowly expiring, and the yellow fans are becoming more important. Data degradation?

It was not expected to literally follow the fib. cycle curve, but that it has is **fascinating!**
Note the cycle used was the same for both

Small 2.5.1 update (b)

Yesterday the company received an unexpected \$7,000 from the SBA - with no strings attached - and we hadn't applied (recently). What was interesting was two things:

1. This enabled the company savings to exceed the 20k loan from before, almost as if the Universe knew the amount of debt (as well as that I had wanted to exceed that number)

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2. It was again company savings, and this is the data leyline we've been tracking. Since this corresponded with the upward move yesterday, I found this *potentially* fascinating.

And yes, I was very grateful to GOD (The Big G). Might it be the result of mimsical whimsy and tracking? Of the experiment? Unknown. But the "coincidence" seems rather interesting give the subject of Luck yesterday in the Threefold Science paper being written.

Sincerely,
Sf. R. Careaga